

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES OF PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE FOREIGN LANGUAGE TEACHERS

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Abstract: The article is based on the methodology of professional development of future foreign language teachers and the specific features of English language teaching, scientific conclusions on improving the quality and efficiency of education by introducing modern innovative technologies into the educational process. In particular, there are a number of advantages of using information and communication technologies in learning a foreign language.

Key words: higher education, innovative method, CEFR, IELTS, humanitarian, Creative Problem Solving, When pictures speak

After the independence of our country, interest in learning English is increasing and many opportunities have been created for young people. As our first president Islam Karimov said, "Currently, teaching foreign languages is given great importance in our country. Today, it is more important than ever for the countries that are trying to take their rightful place in the world community, for our nation, which is building its great future in solidarity with foreign partners, investors, and entrepreneurs. As a logical continuation of these ideas, the decision PQ-2909 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev dated April 20, 2017 "On measures for the further development of the higher education system" improvement of education, in particular, improving the quality of English speaking and listening in humanities students who do not specialize in teaching English in higher education institutions, and ultimately, improving the effectiveness of English language teaching in the continuing education system .

In our republic, new methods and requirements have been developed in accordance with the recommendations of the pan-European frameworks (CEFR, IELTS) for foreign language teaching and assessment of knowledge and skills of foreign language teachers. According to it, textbooks were created for students of general higher education and vocational colleges. In accordance with these requirements, classrooms were equipped with stands and new information and communication techniques. The demand for learning a foreign language is increasing day by day. Foreign language science is divided into four aspects (reading, writing, listening and speaking), and separate concepts and skills are given for each of them.

The role of modern technology in language learning and teaching is incomparable. The use of technological tools is useful in every aspect of learning a foreign language (reading, writing, listening and speaking). For example, to listen and understand, of course, this process cannot be carried out without a computer, player, DVD (CD), SMART TV discs. Listening comprehension is one of the most important parts of language learning. At the same time, the student is required to pay attention to the speaker's pronunciation, adherence to grammatical rules, vocabulary and its meanings. An important factor in the use of modern technologies in

the educational process is that students know and use information and communication technologies well.

Teaching and learning a foreign language using modern technologies is one of the most fruitful ways. In this process, including:

- when using computers, the student can watch and listen to foreign language videos, demonstrations, dialogues, films or cartoons;
- you can listen to and watch foreign language radio broadcasts and television programs;
- SMART TVs can be used.

The use of these technical tools makes the process of foreign language learning more interesting and effective for humanitarian students. Today, teaching through interactive games is becoming a tradition in higher education and higher education institutions. It is known that the lesson is conducted on the basis of various games, which ensures that students demonstrate their abilities, concentrate, improve their knowledge and skills, and become stronger. The basis of the use of game technology activates and accelerates the student.

In pedagogical studies, the psychological mechanisms of playful activity are based on the fundamental needs of a person to express himself, find a stable place in life, self-control, and realize his potential. Any game should be based on generally accepted educational principles and tactics. Educational games should be based on educational subjects. In the process of games, the student is more interested in this exercise than in a regular lesson and performs activities more easily. It should be noted that the game is, first of all, a method of teaching.

Students participate in game lessons with interest, strive to win, and the teacher provides education to the student through them. The student's confidence in being able to speak English increases by playing games. It is known that in the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach students to think independently. Today, English language teachers are using the following innovative methods based on the experience of pedagogues from the United States of America and England:

- To apply this method of "Creative Problem Solving", the beginning of the story is read, and the students' judgment is referred to how it ends;
- "Merry Riddles" teaching riddles to students is important in teaching English, they learn unfamiliar words and find answers to riddles;
- "Quick answers" helps to improve the efficiency of the lesson;
- "Chigil yozdi" ("Warm-up exercises") using various games in the classroom to interest students in the lesson;
- "Pantomime" (pantomime) this method can be used in a lesson where very difficult topics need to be explained or when written exercises are done and students are tired;
- "A chain story" method helps to develop oral speech of students;
- "Acting characters" this method can be used in all types of lessons. In order to teach the profession, people in professions such as "Interpreter", "Translator", "Writer", "Poet" can participate in the class and talk with students;

- "Thinkers meeting" poets and scientists such as U. Shakespeare, A. Navai, Ibn Sina can be "invited". At such a time, using the wise words they said in the lesson will help young people to be educated as perfect people;

- The "When pictures speak" method is very convenient and helps to teach English and develop oral speech of students, for this it is necessary to use pictures related to the topic;

- Quiz cards are distributed according to the number of students and allow all students to participate in the lesson at the same time, which saves time. As we have seen, each innovative technology has its own advantages. In all such methods, cooperation between the teacher and the student and the active movement of the student in the educational process are envisaged.

Today, the leading specialists of our republic have many modern educational materials and multimedia tools that serve to teach foreign languages to the young generation in higher education institutions, to enable them to communicate freely in these languages, and to ensure the quality and effectiveness of foreign language classes. Electronic textbooks have been created and are being used in the educational process. For example, a system of organization based on information and communication technologies was created for teaching English to students of humanitarian education, and one of the most important aspects of this system is its continuous implementation. English teachers should also pay attention to the implementation of didactic rules and regulations in accordance with the specific characteristics of the educational subject during the use of various communication technologies and electronic resources. Because English language science differs from other educational subjects: grammatical topics in the educational process, similar syntactic phenomena, speech skills and competences are taught in a continuous and interconnected manner. Teaching English through information and communication technologies includes:

- teaching vocabulary; working on pronunciation;

- teaching dialogic and monologic speaking;

- teaching writing; - review and analysis of grammatical events. The use of technical tools in English classes helps to solve a number of didactic tasks:

Pupils develop reading skills, improve their writing skills, fill up their vocabulary, increase their interest in learning foreign languages, increase cognitive activity, and broaden their worldview. Also, the teacher can make changes to the task system depending on the interest of the students, for example, dividing the class into small groups, each group is assigned to create texts such as a greeting card, survey, biography, summary. Information and communication technologies, computer programs also provide effective results in the formation of students' English speaking activities. In the implementation of this process, the teacher's creativity is considered important, and if the exercises are combined into various combinations, the foreign language events are mastered by the students, their linguistic abilities are formed, it helps to create communicative situations, the automation of language and speech movements and the students' they are allowed to work independently. A high result can be achieved by using electronic multimedia tools created by experts in English lessons. For example, when teaching students "Grammar 375" section, using computers and audio tools, phonetic exercises can be performed. In this, sounds, words, phrases and sentences are broadcasted to the students on an audio device and received by visual viewing on the screen. Important aspects of the use of such tools are that students also observe the articulatory behavior on the screen, hear and learn the correct pronunciation, and the correct

patterns are retained in their memory. Educational materials presented in multimedia and electronic form allow students to perform grammar exercises individually and as a team, to correctly understand the questions asked by each student, to find the exact answer, to achieve an effective result and to spend a short time. will give. There is another issue that English language experts should pay attention to, which is one of the unique didactic features of foreign language subjects, that is, teaching the student a new topic, new vocabulary in lesson planning. In addition to memorizing, explaining new rules, each student's individual abilities, personality development, and interest in learning a foreign language are considered to be increased. This is achieved by performing the following tasks:

- teaching students to use the knowledge, skills and abilities acquired in the course of teaching English in practice; selection of educational material and tasks taking into account the possibilities, abilities and age characteristics of students; Arouse students' interest in foreign language by means of different forms and methods of teaching, using didactic games prepared on the basis of many educational computer programs: multimedia, repeater, Flash, Microsoft PowerPoint, Microsoft Word, etc. shoot:

- the teacher should pay attention to the ability to ensure the active movement of all students in the planning and organization of the educational process. Because personality is formed in the process of activity. Didactic games prepared with the help of computer equipment (on the basis of multimedia, repeater, Flash, Microsoft Power Point, Microsoft Word, etc.), as we noted above, give effective results in teaching foreign languages to students. Increases their interest in the lesson.

In short, as a result of using innovative methods in English classes, students' logical thinking skills develop, their speech develops, and the ability to quickly and correctly answer is formed. Such methods make the student eager for knowledge. The student tries to prepare thoroughly for classes. This makes students active subjects of the educational process. As the educational system sets itself the task of educating a free-thinking, well-rounded, mature person, in the future, we future teachers will contribute by developing ways to effectively use innovative technologies. possible

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